

Some Recent Developments in Higher-Order Cycloaddition Reactions[†]

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Higher-order cycloaddition reactions provide an easy entry into medium sized ring systems which are often found in a number of important biologically active natural products. In this connection, our investigations on 2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one, an 8π cross-conjugated system, have exposed some novel reactivity patterns including a higher-order cycloaddition profile. The cycloaddition reactions of this electron-deficient heptafulvene system proceeded in an [8+2] fashion with 1,3-dienes, whereas an exclusive [4+2] pathway prevailed with aralkenes. The reactions with cyclic cross-conjugated systems such as pentafulvenes afforded [8+2] and [4+2] adducts, the ratio being controlled by the substitution on the exocyclic double bond of the fulvene. The observed reactivity has been rationalized by theoretical calculations.

The thermal [4+2], photochemical [2+2] cycloaddition reactions have been extensively investigated during the last several decades¹. In contrast, however, higher-order cycloadditions have attracted only scant attention until recently². Noteworthy in this area are the cycloaddition reactions of tropone and its derivatives. The most common reaction pathway of these systems involves a [6+4] mode of addition with dienes³. They are also known to undergo [4+2] as well as [8+2] cycloadditions⁴. Such higher-order cycloaddition reactions of troponoid systems are of great interest both from the synthetic and mechanistic standpoints. These reactions potentially offer rapid access to bicyclo systems having [5.3.0] ring system which is an important structural element of a number of biologically active natural and non-natural compounds⁵.

Fig. 1

properties, but much of the interest in these compounds is concerned with their cycloaddition profiles. The pioneering work carried out by Doering and Wiley in 1954 realized the potential of heptafulvene as an 8π synthon (Scheme 1)⁷.

2*H*-Cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one readily obtained from chlorotropone and diethyl malonate can be viewed as electron-deficient heptafulvene⁸. In contrast to the reaction profiles of electron-rich heptafulvenes, the cycloaddition reactions of such compounds have received only scant atten-

Scheme 1

Heptafulvene⁶ can be considered as an 8π cross-conjugated system analogous to tropone, in which the exocyclic oxygen atom is replaced by a methylene group (Fig. 1).

Heptafulvenes exhibit electrophilic and nucleophilic

tion. Potentially this extended 8π array can participate in cycloaddition reactions in a number of different pathways. Recently the [8+2]cycloaddition reactions of 2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one with electron-rich dienophiles such as

Scheme 2

[†]This paper is dedicated with respectful regards to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

enamines⁹ and vinyl ether analogues¹⁰ have been effectively exploited in the synthesis of various alkyl substituted azulenes (Scheme 2).

In the context of our general interest in cycloaddition reactions, we have investigated the cycloaddition profile of **5** with alkenes, dienes and fulvenes and our results are highlighted in this review.

Cycloaddition reactions with 1,3-dienes

3-Ethoxycarbonyl-2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one (**5**) on treatment with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene at 150° in toluene in a Schlenk glass tube sealed under argon afforded a deep red product **9** in 97% yield¹¹. The reaction is illustrated in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3. Reagent and condition: (i) Toluene, sealed tube, 150° 14 h, 97%

Evidently the formation of the dihydroazulene (**9**) occurs via the initial [8+2]cycloaddition of 3-ethoxycarbonyl-2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene followed by the decarboxylation of the intermediate (Fig. 2).

Fig 2

In order to confirm the proposed regio- and stereochemistry of the dihydroazulene (**9**), it was essential to obtain single crystal X-ray data on a suitable derivative of the latter. For this purpose, **9** was treated with maleic anhydride; reaction proceeded in a [4+2] fashion yielding the *endo*-adduct **11** in 52% yield (Scheme 4). Interestingly, cycloaddition reactions of rigid heptafulvenoid [5.3.0] systems, such as **9** have not been studied previously.

Scheme 4. Reagent and condition: (i) Benzene, sealed tube, 90°, 12 h, 52%.

Final proof for the assigned structure of the adduct and consequently that of the dihydroazulene (**9**) was obtained from single crystal X-ray analysis of **11**.

The [8+2]cycloaddition of **5** with acyclic 1,3-dienes leading to dihydroazulenes appears to be a general reaction. The results obtained with various dienes are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CYCLOADDITION REACTIONS OF **5** WITH ACYCLIC 1,3-DIENES, STYRENES, CYCLOALKYL FULVENES AND DIALKYL FULVENES

Sl No	Diene Dienophile	Product	Condition*	R	Yield%,
1			a	Ph	71**
2			a	Ans	51**
3			b	Me	86**
4			b	—	90**
5			c	OMe	52 (Isomeric ratio, 2.5 : 1)
6			c	Me	80 (Isomeric ratio, 2.4 : 1)
7			c	Cl	88 (Isomeric ratio, 2.5 : 1)
8			d	n=1	47
9			d	n=2	39
10			d	n=3	37
11			d	n=1	43
12			d	n=2	41
13			d	n=3	31
14			d	R=R'=Me	87
15			e	R=H, R'=Me	68
16			e	R=H, R'='Pr	80

*a: Toluene, sealed tube, argon, 130°, 14 h.

b: Xylene, sealed tube, argon, 130°, 5 h

c: Toluene, sealed tube, 140°, 24 h

d: Sealed tube, 150°, 3 h.

e: Sealed tube, 170°, 5 h

**Regio- and stereochemical assignment is based on analogy with 12

Cycloaddition reactions with aralkenes

Subsequent to our investigations on the cycloadditions of **5** with 1,3-dienes, it was of interest to examine the reactivity of **5** towards aralkenes. In particular, we were intrigued

Scheme 5 *Reagent and condition* (i) Toluene, sealed tube, 160°, 20 h, 86%

by the possibility that such reactions can give rise to azulenoids. Additional impetus came from the fact that there has been no information available on the cycloaddition profile of 2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one with aralkenes.

The reaction of 3-ethoxycarbonyl-2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one (5) with acenaphthylene proceeded exclusively in a [4+2]addition mode forming *endo*- and *exo*-adducts (13 and 14) in 86% yield (Scheme 5)¹².

Similarly the reaction of 3-ethoxycarbonyl-2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one with styrene gave 16 as an inseparable mixture of isomers (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6 *Reagent and condition* (i) Toluene, sealed tube, 160°, 24 h, 90%

Similar reactions were observed when 5 was treated with different substituted styrenes. In all these cases, the addition took place only in a [4+2] mode yielding an inseparable mixture of two isomers. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Reaction of 5 with indene also afforded an isomeric mixture of [4+2]adducts 18 in 99% yield based on the unreacted furanone (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7 *Reagent and condition* (i) Toluene, sealed tube, 140°, 24 h, 99%

Cycloaddition reactions with pentafulvenes

The reactions of 5 with pentafulvenes appeared interesting from the standpoint of their potential for higher-order pathways. Except for an isolated report on the reaction of 6,6-dimethylfulvene with 2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one leading predominantly to an [8+2]adduct¹³, there has been no investigations in this area. Therefore, we have studied the reactions of 5 with different 6,6-diaryl-, 6,6-cycloalkyl- and 6,6-dialkylfulvenes¹⁴.

3-Ethoxycarbonyl-2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one (5) on treatment with 6,6-diphenylfulvene yielded both [8+2]- and [4+2]adducts in 16 and 60% yields respectively (Scheme 8).

Similar mode of cycloadditions was also observed in the reactions of 3-ethoxycarbonyl-2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one (5) with various cycloalkylfulvenes (Table 1).

The reactions of 5 with dialkylfulvenes under similar conditions afforded almost exclusively the [8+2] adducts with only trace amounts of [4+2] adducts (Table 1).

Scheme 8 *Reagent and condition* (i) Toluene, sealed tube, 150°, 6 h, 90%

Synthesis of novel colchicinoids

Higher-order cycloaddition reactions of heptafulvenes and their analogs can find a place in the synthesis of biologically active molecules. As a potential application of this chemistry, we have synthesized the cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one derivative of the antimetabolic agent colchicine. Interestingly, the cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one derivative (**22**) underwent a facile [8+2] addition with acyclic 1,3-dienes yielding modified colchicinoids incorporating bicyclo[5.3.0]ring system (Scheme 9)¹¹.

served reactivity of 3-ethoxycarbonyl-2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one with acyclic dienes is given in Fig. 3 using the reaction with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene as an example.

From the orbital coefficients of the reactants it is clear that in the case of [8+2] addition only the interaction between HOMO of cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one and LUMO of 2,3-dimethylbutadiene is symmetry-allowed. It is also noteworthy that the size and sign of the interacting orbitals are perfectly in match for the [8+2] addition mode rather than the competing [4+2] mode. Although energetically slightly

Theoretical considerations

In order to explain the observed reactivity and periselectivity in cycloaddition reactions of 2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one, we have carried out some MNDO calculations using MOPAC version 5. A theoretical rationalization of the ob-

Fig. 3. Molecular orbital correlation diagrams of **5** and 2,3-dimethylbutadiene

Fig. 4. Molecular orbital correlation diagrams of **5** and acenaphthylene

disfavored, the [8+2] cycloaddition is controlled by the HOMO of the cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one.

The correlation diagram for the reaction of 3-ethoxycarbonyl-2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one (**5**) with acenaphthylene is illustrated as an example in Fig. 4. The results revealed that in case of [4+2] addition of 2*H*-cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-

Fig. 5. Molecular orbital correlation diagrams of **5** and 6,6-diphenylfulvene.

one, the reaction proceeds in an inverse electron demand Diels-Alder pathway controlled by NLUMO(furanone)-HOMO(dienophile) interaction. In the case of reactions of cyclohepta[*b*]furan-2-one with pentafulvenes (Fig. 5), it is clear from the correlation diagram that for [8+2] addition, only the interaction of HOMO(furanone)-LUMO(fulvene) is symmetry allowed. It is also observed that the [4+2] addition is controlled by the NLUMO(furanone)-HOMO(fulvene) interaction.

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